

Optimization of GA₃ Concentrations and Growing Conditions on the Survival and Economic Performance of Softwood Grafts in Tamarind (*Tamarindus indica* L.) Cv. No. 263

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Abstract

An experiment conducted to assess the effects of different GA₃ concentrations and growing conditions on the survival and economics of tamarind softwood grafts. The treatment (T₂) GA₃ 100 ppm + green shadenet house found superior in terms of maximum survival percentage (79.47%) at 120 DAG. The satisfactory outcome in respect to the higher grafts success in tamarind Cv. No. 263 with gross returns (Rs.3814), net income (Rs.2446) and maximum B:C ratio (2.78) was also recorded in the same treatment.

Keywords: Economics, GA₃, graft survival, growing condition, tamarind

Introduction

Tamarind (*Tamarindus indica* L.) belongs to the family Leguminosae, subfamily Caesalpiniaceae is native to tropical Africa. Tamarind tree grows wild, though cultivated to limited extent. Tamarind can be propagated by several vegetative methods, including stem cuttings, budding, inarching, air layering, softwood grafting, and veneer grafting. In India softwood grafting method is being employed on commercial scale for production of planting material in tamarind. These tamarind grafts perform well initially, but over the time, the mortality rate increases and development becomes extremely slow, as is the case with softwood grafting in open conditions. To overcome this bottleneck in tamarind grafting, application of GA₃ at different concentrations and optimized growing conditions are necessary for better growth and survival. The GA₃ involves in synthesis of amylase and other hydrolytic enzymes during the sprouting process. It is considered the principal factor activating gluconeogenic enzymes in the early phases of grafting. Favourable weather conditions are essential for the success of tamarind grafts because they may cause early vascular tissue contact and cambium layer formation, which trigger early sprouting. The optimal temperature for tamarind graft growth ranges from 28°C to 34°C, with green shade net houses proving most effective. Hence, it is advantageous to use a shadenet house to enhance propagation efficiency and to increase survival rates. A critical review of existing literature indicates significant potential for utilizing GA₃ and varying growing environments to further improve the growth and success rates of softwood grafts in tamarind. In light of this, the present investigation was designed with the objective of evaluating the effects of different GA₃ concentrations and growing conditions on the survival rate and economic performance of softwood grafts in tamarind Cv. No. 263.

Materials and methods

The present investigation entitled “Optimization of GA₃ concentrations and growing conditions on the survival and economic performance of softwood grafts in tamarind (*Tamarindus indica* L.) Cv. No. 263” was carried out at Central Nursery, Vasantnao Naik Marathwada Krishi Vidyapeeth, Parbhani during the year 2024-2025. The experiment was laid out in randomized block design with ten treatments replicated thrice.

Table 1: Treatment details

Treatments	Treatment details
T ₁	GA ₃ @ 100 ppm + Open condition
T ₂	GA ₃ @ 100 ppm + Green shadenet house
T ₃	GA ₃ @ 100 ppm + White shadenet house
T ₄	GA ₃ @ 125 ppm + Open condition
T ₅	GA ₃ @ 125 ppm + Green shadenet house
T ₆	GA ₃ @ 125 ppm + White shadenet house
T ₇	GA ₃ @ 150 ppm + Open condition
T ₈	GA ₃ @ 150 ppm + Green shadenet house
T ₉	GA ₃ @ 150 ppm + White shadenet house
T ₁₀	Control

The bud sticks were collected during morning hours and kept in wet gunny bags to conserve moisture. The bud sticks were selected suitable to the thickness of rootstocks. The top of the stem was split longitudinally to about 4-5 cm in length forming a V shape. The lower end of the scion was cut into gently sloping wedge of about 3 to 4 cm by removing the bark and wood from both the opposite sides. The wedge shaped scion stick was inserted into the V shaped split of the rootstock and secured firmly with 200-gauge thickness green transparent polythene strip. The local rootstock was collected for tamarind grafting. The grafts were treated with foliar application of GA₃ at different concentration at 30 and 60 DAG and with soil drenching of Biomix 4% immediately after grafting. The grafts were then maintained under different growing conditions such as open condition, green shadenet house and white shadenet house for assessing growth and success of tamarind grafts.

Results and Discussion:

The perusal of the data presented in Table 2 and 3 regarding survival and economics of tamarind grafts as influenced by different concentrations of GA₃ and growing conditions recorded significant differences.

Survival percent of grafts

The data pertaining to survival percentage of graft revealed that treatment (T₂) GA₃ 100 ppm + green shadenet house had maximum survival percent of grafts (79.47%) among rest of the treatments under study while the minimum survival percent (51.67%) was recorded in (T₁₀) control. The highest percentage of survival may be attributed due to the foliar applications of GA₃, which increases final graft survival primarily by accelerating and strengthening graft union formation. The GA₃ at 100 ppm concentration optimally enhanced vascular reconnection at the graft union by balancing auxin and GA₃ crosstalk, whereas higher dose (125 and 150 ppm) disrupted hormonal equilibrium, causing poor callus formation and resource diversion to shoots at the expense of root development.

This is in conformity with the findings of Pawar *et al.* (2018) [10] and Dhorajiya *et al.* (2022) [4]. The above results might be due to favourable microclimatic conditions, such as moderate temperature and relative humidity inside for a longer period, which prevented desiccation of the scion and promoting stronger graft union that helped for better survival of the grafts. The mentioned result is in accordance with Raghavendra *et al.* (2011) [12], Chander *et al.* (2016) [2], Manga *et al.* (2017) [8], Nanditha *et al.* (2017) [9], Laxmi *et al.* (2018) [6], Mahesh *et al.* (2018) [7], Anil *et al.* (2022) [1] and Dewangan *et al.* (2023) [3].

Table 2: Effect of GA₃ concentrations and growing conditions on final survival percent of grafts in tamarind at 120 DAG

Treatment No.	Final survival % of graft
T ₁	61.67
T ₂	79.47
T ₃	70.00
T ₄	57.67
T ₅	71.67
T ₆	73.33
T ₇	58.33
T ₈	75.57
T ₉	67.35
T ₁₀	51.67
SE ±	2.03
CD @ 5%	6.02

*Each value is average of three determination

Economic parameters

The economics and B:C ratio of grafts were evaluated. The data show that treatment T₂ (GA₃ 100 ppm + green shadenet house) provided the highest gross returns (Rs. 3814) and net returns (Rs. 2446), whereas the lowest gross (Rs. 2480) and net returns (Rs. 1234) were noted in treatment T₁₀ (control). This may be attributed to the grafts receiving an optimal concentration of GA₃ and being maintained under favorable microclimatic conditions in the green shadenet house, which improved survivability and ultimately resulted in the highest net returns for this treatment. These results are in accordance with findings by Ghuge *et al.* (2023) [5] and Priyanka *et al.* (2023) [11] in tamarind, who reported similar effects of GA₃ and environmental conditions on graft success. Furthermore, this investigation revealed that the B:C ratio was significantly influenced by both GA₃ concentration and growing conditions. The highest B:C ratio (2.78) was recorded in Treatment T₂ (GA₃ 100 ppm + green shadenet house), while the lowest (1.97) was observed in the T₁₀ (Control).

Table 3: Effect of GA₃ concentrations and growing conditions on economics and B:C ratio of tamarind graft at 120 DAG

Treatments	Survival percent (%)	Selling Price (Rs/graft)	Cost of production for 60 grafts (Rs)	Treatment cost for 60 grafts (Rs)	Total cost for 60 grafts Production (Rs)	Gross return (Rs)	Net Return (Rs)	B:C ratio
T ₁	61.67	80	1246	118	1364	2960	1596	2.17
T ₂	79.47	80	1246	122	1368	3814	2446	2.78
T ₃	70.00	80	1246	126	1372	3360	1988	2.44
T ₄	57.67	80	1246	128	1374	2768	1394	2.01
T ₅	71.67	80	1246	132	1378	3440	2062	2.49
T ₆	73.33	80	1246	136	1382	3519	2128	2.54
T ₇	58.33	80	1246	143	1389	2799	1410	2.02
T ₈	75.57	80	1246	147	1393	3627	2234	2.60
T ₉	67.35	80	1246	151	1397	3232	1835	2.31
T ₁₀	51.67	80	1246	00	1246	2480	1234	1.97

Conclusion:

The foliar application of gibberellic acid (GA₃) at 100 ppm at 30 and 60 days after grafting (DAG), with grafts maintained under green shadenet house conditions, demonstrated significant superiority over all other treatments. This combination resulted in enhanced survivability and better economic returns for softwood grafts in tamarind Cv.No.263. These results highlight that optimizing GA₃ concentration, along with providing a favourable microclimate such as green shadenet house; can greatly enhance grafting outcomes and profitability.

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